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PROGRAM INTERNATIONAL SECTION

II Youth Forum Insolvency (Bankruptcy): New Problems and Challenges

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Law School of Moscow State University M.V. Lomonosov

(Address: Moscow, Leninskie Gory, 1, Buildings 13–14, 4th Academic Building)

THE EFFECTS OF INSOLVENCY ON COMMERCIAL ACTIVITY

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CONTENT

First: Contracts in respect of which insolvency is declared before their performance is completed.

Second: Contracts of Sale

Third: Lease Contracts

Fourth: Employment Contracts

Fifth: Administrative Contracts, Licenses, and Concession Rights

- Individuals and business entities may encounter financial distress in the course of their commercial activities, potentially leading to insolvency, such as the cessation of debt payments or situations where liabilities exceed assets. Such circumstances adversely affect creditors and disrupt economic activity. Accordingly, the Jordanian legislator has addressed this condition through the Insolvency Law, with the aim of safeguarding the debtor's estate while ensuring a fair balance with the rights of creditors.
- The declaration of insolvency gives rise to legal consequences affecting the debtor's contracts and dispositions. Certain contracts may continue under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, whereas others may be restricted or deemed void, particularly if concluded during specified periods preceding or following the declaration of insolvency, in order to preserve the integrity of the debtor's estate.
- Moreover, the Jordanian Insolvency Law seeks to rehabilitate financially distressed enterprises by facilitating the restructuring of their debts through negotiated settlements with creditors. This approach enables such entities to maintain their operations and recover their investments. The law further provides legal protection to the debtor and limits the premature liquidation of assets, while establishing equitable mechanisms for debt settlement. Ultimately, these measures contribute to economic stability and enhance confidence in the investment environment.

INTRODUCTION

- An important question arises here, given that a merchant enters into various commercial contracts. If the merchant experiences financial distress that prevents them from fulfilling contractual obligations and debts, and is subsequently declared insolvent, does the declaration of insolvency affect the contracts concluded prior to the court's decision?
- This issue will be examined by analyzing these contracts according to their different types, as follows:

SECTION ONE EFFECT OF DECLARING INSOLVENCY ON ONGOING CONTRACTS

FIRST: CONTRACTS IN RESPECT OF WHICH INSOLVENCY IS DECLARED BEFORE THEIR PERFORMANCE IS COMPLETED.

These contracts were concluded prior to the declaration of insolvency, and the parties had already begun their performance. However, insolvency was declared before their completion. The effects of such contracts are not limited to the debtor and creditors alone, but also extend to third parties who are connected to the merchant through these agreements.

Accordingly, the Insolvency Law provides that:

"The declaration of insolvency shall not affect the continuation of contracts under execution. For the purposes of this Law, an ongoing contract is defined as a contract where neither the debtor nor the other party has completed its performance as of the date of the insolvency declaration" (Article 27/A of the Insolvency Law).

Therefore, the Insolvency Law regulates ongoing contracts and determines how they should be handled and how the parties involved are treated. It grants the debtor, under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, or the insolvency trustee himself, the right to act. This right also extends to the other party to the contract, allowing them to request the continuation of the contract's performance,

AS STIPULATED BY THE INSOLVENCY LAW:

"1. The insolvency trustee, or the debtor under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, as the case may be, may continue the performance of an ongoing contract and may require the other party to fully perform its obligations.

2. The other party may request the insolvency trustee, or the debtor under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, to make a decision regarding their intention to continue the performance of the contract within five days from the date of notification of the request; otherwise, the right to do so shall lapse."

(Article 27/B of the Insolvency Law)

<p>Termination of Ongoing Contracts</p> <p>If termination serves the interests of insolvency proceedings:</p> <p>The insolvency trustee (or debtor under supervision) may terminate the contract .</p> <p>Legal effect:</p> <p>Both parties are released from remaining obligations.</p> <p>Impact on the other party:</p> <p>May suffer financial damage</p> <p>Has the right to claim compensation</p> <p>Legal status of compensation:</p>		
<p>Considered an unsecured insolvency debt</p>		
<p>Added to the list of creditors.</p>	<p>Legal Basis Article 27/C – Jordanian Insolvency Law</p>	<p>8</p>

It should be noted that when the Insolvency Law regulates the provisions, it establishes that any prior contractual clause stipulating termination of the contract upon the declaration of insolvency shall be deemed void.

In this regard, the Insolvency Law provides that:

"Any clause in a contract to which the debtor is a party shall be deemed null and void if it grants the other party the right to terminate the contract or provides for its automatic termination upon the declaration of the debtor's insolvency or any equivalent proceedings."

(Article 28 of the Insolvency Law)

- The contracts concluded by a merchant prior to the declaration of insolvency are diverse. They may include contracts of sale, construction contracts, lease agreements, and others, as required by the nature of commercial activity through which the merchant seeks to operate their business and achieve profits and interests.
- However, the contract of sale has a particular nature that distinguishes it from other contracts. In a sale, the contract may be concluded while the delivery of the goods or the payment of the price is subject to the agreement of the parties or to commercial custom. Accordingly, if a sale contract is concluded but its obligations—namely the delivery of the goods or payment of the price—have not yet been performed, the contract may be rescinded.
- In this regard, the Insolvency Law provides that:
- *"The insolvency trustee, or the debtor under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, may request the rescission of a sale contract concluded prior to the declaration of insolvency, provided that the goods have not been delivered or the price has not been paid."*
(Article 29/A of the Insolvency Law)

SECOND: CONTRACTS OF SALE

Furthermore, the law grants the seller, in a sale contract concluded prior to the declaration of insolvency—where the debtor is the buyer—the right to withhold delivery of the goods until the price is paid, unless the contract provides otherwise.

The law states:

*"A seller who has not received the agreed price may refrain from delivering the goods until the debtor pays the price or complies with the terms of the contract concluded with him."
(Article 29/B of the Insolvency Law)*

However, if the seller has received part of the price, they are not entitled to withhold part of the goods corresponding to the unpaid amount. In such a case, either the contract must be performed in full or rescinded entirely, in order to avoid causing harm to the debtor who is already facing exceptional circumstances due to insolvency. Accordingly, the law provides:

*"If the seller has received part of the price, they shall not have the right to retain or recover only the goods corresponding to the unpaid portion."
(Article 29/C of the Insolvency Law)*

- Lease contracts are characterized as time-based agreements, meaning they are performed over a period of time. Therefore, some lease contracts may still be ongoing at the time of the declaration of insolvency. Accordingly, the Insolvency Law provides for the continuation of lease contracts unless their termination serves the interests of the insolvency proceedings.
- In this regard, the law states:
- *"Notwithstanding any other legislation, and subject to the provisions of paragraph (D) of this Article, a lessor shall not be entitled to terminate a lease agreement for premises occupied by the debtor due to the declaration of insolvency. However, the insolvency trustee, or the debtor under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, may terminate any lease agreement prior to its expiry if such termination serves the interests of the insolvency proceedings. In such case, the debtor shall be liable to pay the rent due up to the date of vacating the premises."
(Article 30/A of the Insolvency Law)*

THIRD: LEASE CONTRACTS

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Lease termination and continuation in insolvency proceedings

However, the interests of the insolvency proceedings may require terminating the lease. Therefore, the law grants the insolvency trustee, or the debtor under supervision, the authority to decide whether to continue or terminate the lease.

If the lease continues, the law distinguishes between rent due before and after the declaration of insolvency:

Rent due **before insolvency** is considered a debt against the insolvency estate and is treated like other insolvency debts.

Rent due **after insolvency**, where continuation is requested, is considered a debt arising from insolvency proceedings and is treated as an expense of those proceedings.

The law provides:

"The insolvency trustee, or the debtor under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, as the case may be, shall notify the lessor of their intention either to terminate the lease agreement or to continue its performance for a specified period. If the lease continues, the rent due thereafter shall be considered debts arising from insolvency proceedings and shall be paid when due in accordance with this Law, while amounts due prior to the declaration of insolvency shall be considered debts against the insolvency estate."

(Article 30/B of the Insolvency Law)

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These provisions apply whether the leased property is movable or immovable. The law states:

"The provisions of this Article shall apply where the leased movable or immovable assets are necessary for the continuation of business or the conduct of insolvency proceedings. Otherwise, the lessor may terminate the contract unless adequate guarantees are provided to secure payment of the rent."

(Article 30/C of the Insolvency Law)

- With regard to employment contracts, the law—while taking into account all parties involved in the event of the debtor's insolvency—also considers the protection of employees. Accordingly, it provides that:
- *"The declaration of insolvency shall not affect valid employment contracts."
(Article 31/A of the Insolvency Law)*
- However, there may be a need to modify or terminate certain employment contracts. Therefore, the law grants the insolvency trustee, or the debtor under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, the right to request the amendment or termination of all or some employment contracts.
- In such cases, the court is required to hear the opinion of the employees or their representatives before making a decision, in order to ensure fairness and avoid prejudice to any party. The law states:
- *"Notwithstanding any other legislation, the insolvency trustee, or the debtor under the supervision of the insolvency trustee, may request the court to amend or terminate employment contracts after hearing the opinion of the employees or their representatives."
(Article 31/B of the Insolvency Law)*

FOURTH: EMPLOYMENT CONTRACTS

- Administrative contracts, licenses, and concession rights hold particular importance for the debtor. Therefore, their immediate termination may cause significant harm. Accordingly, the Insolvency Law provides that:
- *"The declaration of insolvency shall not automatically result in the termination of administrative contracts, licenses, or concession rights. However, the contracting authority may terminate the contract, concession right, or revoke the license based on objective reasons that justify concerns regarding non-performance. The mere declaration of insolvency shall not be sufficient grounds for termination as long as the debtor's economic activity continues."
(Article 32/A of the Insolvency Law)*

FIFTH: ADMINISTRATIVE CONTRACTS, LICENSES, AND CONCESSION RIGHTS

This approach also reflects the importance of ensuring the continuity of public services, as such contracts, licenses, or concessions may relate to the provision of essential public services. Therefore, to safeguard the uninterrupted delivery of these services, the law grants the relevant authority the right to take necessary measures, such as requiring the debtor to continue performance, terminating the contract, appointing a supervisor to act on behalf of the debtor, or adopting other appropriate actions.

The law states:

***"If the contract relates to the management of a public facility or the provision of an essential public service, the authority may take any necessary measures to ensure the continuity of the service."
(Article 32/B of the Insolvency Law)***

EFFECTS OF THE DECLARATION OF INSOLVENCY ON TRANSACTIONS PRIOR TO THE DECLARATION OF INSOLVENCY

- **Effects on Prior Transactions**

General rule:

Effects apply to **post-insolvency transactions**

- **Exception (1-Year Rule)**

Transactions within **1 year before insolvency**:

May be invalidated

If harmful or preferential

- **Legal Basis:**

Article 33/A

- **Harmful Transactions**

Occur when: Debtor receives much less value

One creditor is favored over others

- **Legal Basis:**

Article 33/B

EFFECTS OF THE DECLARATION OF INSOLVENCY ON TRANSACTIONS PRIOR TO THE DECLARATION OF INSOLVENCY

- **Examples of Harm**

- Gifts / no consideration
- Early payment of debts
- Transactions with related parties
- Granting new securities
- Paying secured debts early

- **Valid Transactions (Exceptions)**

- Good faith transactions
- Ordinary course of business
- Protected financial guarantees
- **Legal Basis:**
Article 33/C

EFFECTS OF THE DECLARATION OF INSOLVENCY ON TRANSACTIONS PRIOR TO THE DECLARATION OF INSOLVENCY

SUSPENSION OF ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

- **Suspension of Economic Activity**

One of the **most important effects** of insolvency

Impact

Stops business operations Affects:

- Debtor
- Employees
- Suppliers

Why Suspension?

Focus on insolvency procedures

- Prevent new debts
- Reduce financial burden

Decision Authority

Court decision

Based on request from:

- Debtor
- Insolvency trustee

THANK YOU

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